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1 **The Madrid Affective Database for Spanish (MADS): Ratings of Dominance,**
2 **Familiarity, Subjective Age of Acquisition and Sensory Experience.**

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16 **Short title:** MADS scores for Dominance, Familiarity, AoA, SERs

17

18 **Abstract**

19 The current study presents ratings by 540 Spanish native speakers for dominance,
20 familiarity, subjective age of acquisition (AoA), and sensory experience (SER) for the
21 875 Spanish words included in the Madrid Affective Database for Spanish (MADS).

22 The norms can be downloaded as supplementary materials for this manuscript from
23 [https://www.dropbox.com/s/had01nen8ish9f7/Hinojosa%20et%20al. Supplementary%
24 20materials.xlsx?dl=0](https://www.dropbox.com/s/had01nen8ish9f7/Hinojosa%20et%20al.%20Supplementary%20materials.xlsx?dl=0). These ratings may be of potential relevance to researches who
25 are interested in characterizing the interplay between language and emotion.

26 Additionally, with the aim of investigating how the affective features interact with the
27 lexicosemantic properties of words, we performed correlational analyses between norms
28 for familiarity, subjective AoA and SER, and scores for those affective variables which
29 are currently included in the MADs. A distinct pattern of significant correlations with
30 affective features was found for different lexicosemantic variables. These results show
31 that familiarity, subjective AoA and SERs may have independent effects on the
32 processing of emotional words. They also suggest that these psycholinguistic variables
33 should be fully considered when formulating theoretical approaches to the processing of
34 affective language.

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- 40 **Keywords:** Emotion ratings; Affective dimensions; Discrete emotions; Dominance;
- 41 Familiarity; Subjective age of acquisition; Sensory experience ratings (SERs)

42 **1. Introduction**

43 Most studies exploring the interdependence between language and emotion have been
44 based on the assumptions of dimensional models that conceptualize emotions along
45 three dimensions [1, 2]. The valence dimension represents the polarity of the emotion
46 (ranging from pleasant to unpleasant), whereas the dimension of arousal reflects its
47 intensity (ranging from calming to exciting). A third dimension, dominance, refers to
48 the degree of control experienced by an individual over a stimulus (ranging from out of
49 control to in control). From a different theoretical point of view, discrete-emotion
50 proposals assume a limited number of innate and universal emotional categories, which
51 mainly include happiness, anger, fear, sadness and disgust [3, 4, 5].

52 Developments in the field of the interplay between emotion and language would
53 not have been possible without the publication of several normative databases in
54 different languages. These norming studies have mainly provided ratings for the
55 affective dimensions of valence and arousal. In this sense, the Affective Norms for
56 English words (ANEW) [1] reports scores for 1034 words in the dimensions of valence,
57 arousal and dominance. This corpus has been adapted to multiple languages including
58 Italian [6], Spanish [7] or European Portuguese [8]. Besides, valence and arousal norms
59 for different sets of words have been reported in several studies (German: [9, 10];
60 English: [11, 12]; French:[13]; Dutch: [14, 15, 16]; Finnish: [17, 18]; Polish: [19];
61 Spanish [20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25]). By contrast, normative studies collecting word ratings
62 for discrete emotional categories are rather scarce (English: [26, 27]; German: [28];
63 Spanish [24;29]).

64 The majority of the aforementioned studies provided ratings not only for
65 affective variables but also for several non-emotional psycholinguistic. Besides
66 reporting objective measures based on corpus statistics -such as word frequency, word

67 length or orthographic neighborhood-, ratings for several subjective variables including
68 concreteness [14, 6], imageability [30, 15], familiarity [31, 22, 7] or subjective age of
69 acquisition (AoA) [11, 16] have been collected. Based on these data, it has been
70 possible to outline some conclusions regarding the interplay between emotion and
71 language at both the word and sentence levels. In this sense, the results of several
72 studies have revealed the involvement of lexico-semantic, phonological or
73 morphosyntactic information on the processing of emotional language [32, 33, 34, 35,
74 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45]. However, there are many other questions that
75 remain less understood, such as the effects of subjective AoA in the processing of
76 affective language.

77 The goal of the current study was twofold. As a first objective we aimed to
78 collect ratings for additional subjective affective and psycholinguistic variables for the
79 875 emotional words included in the Madrid Affective Dataset (MADs, [24]), which
80 currently includes norms for the affective dimensions of valence and arousal, as well as
81 for the discrete dimensions of happiness, fear, anger, sadness and disgust and the lexical
82 variable of concreteness. Scores on new affective and lexicosemantic dimensions may
83 be a useful tool to for designing experiments that address unanswered theoretical and
84 methodological questions on the interplay between language and emotion. In particular,
85 ratings for the following variables were collected in the current normative study:

86 • *Dominance*. As previously noted, dominance can be defined in terms of feelings
87 of control over an event as opposed to a feeling of being controlled by a situation.
88 Compared to the dimensions of valence and arousal, the dominance dimension is
89 characterized by specific vocal responses and action tendencies, such as wanting to
90 take initiative versus being apathetic [46]. Nonetheless, to the best of our knowledge

91 the role of dominance on the interactions between language and emotion has been
92 not considered.

93 • *Familiarity*. Familiarity may be defined as the experience that an individual has
94 with a given word [47]. Although familiarity may be related to word frequency, it
95 has been found to be a better predictor of verbal performance than frequency [48].
96 Also, dissociable contributions of frequency and familiarity have been reported in
97 lexical decision and naming tasks [49; 50]. Finally, it has been shown that words
98 showing a similar frequency varied widely in familiarity, and vice versa [51 ; 52].
99 Interestingly, prior studies have established the existence of a relationship between
100 affective dimensions and familiarity [6, 22, 12]. Thus, it may be relevant to consider
101 this variable when designing experiments addressing the processing of affective
102 language.

103 • *Subjective AoA*, This psycholinguistic variable represents the average
104 chronological age at which a particular word is first learned. Although this
105 measure is based on adult estimates of when different words were learned, the
106 results of several studies have shown that rated AoA and objective AoA -based on
107 children's naming performance- show a comparable predictive power for picture
108 naming [53; but see, 54]. Also, AoA effects on word comprehension and production
109 tasks have been shown to differ from those elicited by word frequency or familiarity
110 [55; 56; 57; 58; see 59 for review]. Importantly, several studies have reported
111 specific effects of subjective AoA during the access to orthographic, phonological
112 and semantic representations in non-emotional language [60, 61]. Thus, having
113 available current ratings may be suitable for directly addressing the influence of the
114 age at which words were learned on affective language processing.

115 • *Sensory experience ratings (SERs)*. Sensory experience is a recently developed
116 concept that refers to “the extent to which a word evokes a sensory and/or perceptual
117 experience in the mind of the reader” ([62], p. 160). Although it may be closely
118 related to imageability, it has been suggested that imageability is biased towards
119 visual sensory activation, whereas SERs captures this information along with other
120 sensory modalities [62, 63]. Interestingly, this variable is a reliable predictor of
121 lexical decision response times [64]. So far, there are currently no available data for
122 this variable for affective words. Interestingly, these norms may be of potential
123 interest for researches investigating affective language under the grounded/emodied
124 cognition perspective of semantic representation, which assumes that conceptual
125 processing is rooted in the individual’s perceptual and motor experiences [65, 66, 67,
126 68, 69, 70]).

127 A second goal of this study was to explore the relations between the norms for
128 dominance collected here and the scores for both affective dimensions and discrete
129 emotions that are currently available in the MADs through regression and correlational
130 analyses. Prior work generally showed that people associates feelings of power to
131 highly pleasant and unpleasant words [6, 16, 10]. Also, the relation between dominance
132 and discrete emotions was investigated in a previous study [26], which found that words
133 with higher ratings in happiness, anger, sadness, fear and disgust also scored higher in
134 the dominance dimension.

135 Additionally, we investigated if the emotional impact of a word is likely to be
136 modulated by other lexicosemantic features. For this purpose we examined the relation
137 between the ratings on the affective variables of the MADs- those previously available
138 and the one currently collected- and these collected in the present study for the
139 psycholinguistic variables of familiarity, subjective AoA and SERs. To the best of our

140 knowledge the relationship between discrete emotions and either familiarity, subjective
141 AoA or SERs remains unexplored. In contrast, prior work has shown a relation between
142 familiarity and both dominance and valence. In this sense, whereas people felt more
143 dominant and happier with concepts denoted by words which they are familiar [6, 22,
144 11, 12], unfamiliar words tend to be perceived as being more exciting [12; but see 11].
145 Modulations in the use of emotional language by the AoA of the words have been also
146 described. In this sense, children start using concepts in a broad sense –including all
147 emotions of the same valence-, and then gradually narrow to the use of discrete
148 emotions over a relatively long period of years [71, 72]. Also, words estimated to have
149 been learned at early stages have found to be mainly pleasant, calm and dominant in
150 previous research [11, 12]. Finally, although the relation between SERs and affective
151 dimensions has deserved little attention, previous evidence indicates a positive
152 correlation between valence and some sensory features, such as vivid colors or pleasant
153 taste. Also, high arousal ratings have been associated with words denoting unpleasant
154 taste [12]. Thus, we expected that the results of the correlational analyses reveal the
155 existence of a complex and independent pattern of relations between different
156 lexicosemantic and emotional variables, which make guide future empirical studies on
157 the interplay between language and emotion.

158 **2. Materials and Methods**

159 *2.1. Participants*

160 Data from 540 native Spanish participants (398 females, 142 males; mean age = 24.31
161 years, *S.D.* = 9.03) were collected. Most of them were students from two universities in
162 Madrid (Universidad Complutense and Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia,
163 UNED), but several nonstudent participants took part in the normative study as well.
164 They participated in the study either voluntarily or in exchange for extra course credits.

165 Ratings were collected between February 2014 and September 2014). The study was
166 conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the ethics
167 committee of the Instituto Pluridisciplinar, UCM, Madrid, Spain. Written informed
168 consent was obtained from all participants.

169 *2.2. Materials and procedure*

170 This study used the word-set that was previously selected for [24]. The total 875
171 Spanish words were randomly distributed into 9 lists of 97(\pm 1) words. Two different
172 types of questionnaires per list were created using the SurveyMonkey Web software,
173 making it a total of 18 questionnaires. The links to the online surveys were randomly
174 distributed among our sample, so that 30 participants rated each one of them.

175 One of the versions of the questionnaires collected ratings for familiarity and
176 dominance and was completed by half of the participants. The other version collected
177 the subjective AoA and SERs from the remaining half of the participants. Both of them
178 began with a page that contained some initial demographic questions (age and sex) and
179 explained the nature of the study, which included an estimate of completion time (20-25
180 minutes). Data confidentiality was also addressed here and an e-mail contact was
181 included, in case any of the participants wanted to enquire about our research. Finally,
182 they were provided with the instructions for completion of the ratings for each variable,
183 which were adapted from [1] for dominance, [22] for familiarity, [73] for subjective
184 AoA and [64] for sensory experience, respectively. The instructions that were used can
185 be found in the Appendix.

186 After the initial page, the questionnaires were designed so that each word would
187 be presented alone in each page, in the center of the screen, in black 14-point Helvetica
188 bold font. Below the stimulus words were the two relevant variables to rate. In the
189 familiarity and dominance questionnaire, both dimensions had a 9-point scale and

190 familiarity was fixed as the first variable to rate, in order to prevent that participants felt
191 more familiar with the concepts if words were previously rated for dominance. In the
192 case of the scale of dominance, the instructions included a pictorial depiction of the
193 Self-assessment Manikin (SAM). This is a widely used tool in the assessment of the
194 emotional attributes of stimuli. The dominance scale shows SAM ranging from a very
195 small to a very large figure representing a feeling of being either submissive or
196 powerful, respectively [74]. In the subjective AoA and SERs version, subjective AoA
197 was fixed as the first variable to rate, using an 11-point scale in which 1 meant “less
198 than 2 years old”, numbers 2-10 indicated the ages 2-10, and a score of 11 meant “11
199 years or older” [73]. For the SERs variable, a 7-point scale was chosen [63, 47], with
200 the greater numbers indicating a larger degree of sensory experience. All of the items
201 included a response option labeled “I don’t know the meaning” (mean responses per
202 word = 0.25, $SD = 1.09$).

203 The order of presentation of the words was randomized for each participant in all
204 of the questionnaires. It was also set that once the ratings for a word were submitted,
205 participants were not allowed to go back and change them. Labels were provided to the
206 extreme values in each of the scales, and to all of the values in the subjective AoA scale,
207 to remind the raters of the direction of the polarity of the dimensions.

208 **3. Results and discussion**

209 *3.1. The data base*

210 The descriptive statistics for dominance, familiarity, subjective AoA and SERs are
211 summarized in Table 1. This corpus can be accessed as supplementary material from
212 [https://www.dropbox.com/s/had01nen8ish9f7/Hinojosa%20et%20al._Supplementary%](https://www.dropbox.com/s/had01nen8ish9f7/Hinojosa%20et%20al._Supplementary%20materials.xlsx?dl=0)
213 [20materials.xlsx?dl=0](https://www.dropbox.com/s/had01nen8ish9f7/Hinojosa%20et%20al._Supplementary%20materials.xlsx?dl=0).

214

Table 1 Descriptive stimulus characteristics				
	Dominance	Familiarity	Subjective AoA	SERs
Mean	5.13	5.78	7.07	3.80
SD	1.20	1.16	2.16	0.85
Minimum	2.27	2.24	1.53	1.48
Maximum	8.33	8.60	10.88	6.20
Range	6.06	6.36	9.35	4.72

215

216 *3.1.1. Reliability and validity*

217 The reliability of the values for dominance, familiarity, subjective AoA and sensory
 218 experience was determined according to the split-half intergroup procedure. Participants
 219 were randomly divided into two subgroups of equal size for each version of the
 220 questionnaires. Thereafter, we calculated the Pearson correlation coefficients between
 221 participant's scores for the four variables. The adjusted correlations using the
 222 Spearman–Brown formula were very high for all the variables. For the dominance
 223 dimension, the mean correlation value was $r = .89$ (ranging from $r = .76$ to $.94$). The
 224 split-half reliability for dominance was similar to that found for the arousal dimension
 225 in our prior study ($r = .89$) and lower compared to the correlation observed for the
 226 valence dimension ($r = .94$). These findings agree with the results of prior studies [6, 16,
 227 12] and indicate that ratings for arousal and dominance presented more variability than
 228 those collected for the valence dimension. High correlations were also observed for
 229 subjective AoA (mean $r = .98$, ranging from $r = .97$ to $.99$), familiarity (mean $r = .94$,
 230 ranging from $r = .93$ to $.96$) and SERs (mean $r = .90$, ranging from $r = .85$ to $.96$),
 231 which are in line with the results of previous normative studies [22, 11, 16, 12, 23, 63].

232 With regard to validity, we compared subjective AoA and familiarity values for
 233 some of the words included in our database that have already been rated in other
 234 normative studies. Sensory experience values have not been previously collected in

235 Spanish, so we were not able to compare our scores with any other sources. We also
236 could not conduct any validity analysis for the dominance dimension, since ratings for
237 this dimension are currently available for only 16 of the words included in the MADs
238 [7]. The number of words that have been not previously scored in Spanish was 859 for
239 dominance, 459 for familiarity and 240 for subjective AoA. It should be noted that
240 ratings which were already available came from different corpora, so providing scores
241 collected in a homogenous way for the four variables and incorporating them to the
242 same database may be advantageous [23]. For our subjective AoA scores we observed
243 high positive correlations with the ratings of [73], $r(417) = .95, p < .001$, and [23],
244 $r(294) = .95, p < .001$). The databases by [75] and [76] reported subjective AoA for
245 Spanish words. However, they only included 26 and 0 words, respectively, which were
246 also scored in our corpus. Thus, no reliable results regarding validity could be derived
247 from a direct comparison between scores in these normative studies and those provided
248 here.

249 Also, familiarity ratings were compared with those reported in the study of [23],
250 $r(134) = .77, p < .001$), as well as with those found in the Espal [77], $r(404) = .59, p <$
251 $.001$). Again, even though ratings for familiarity for 8 words that were also included in
252 our normative study were provided in [22], the small number of words shared by the
253 two corpora does not allow to reliably estimating validity. Altogether, the results of
254 these analyses suggest that our data show a high degree of consistency with ratings for
255 the same variables collected in prior normative studies, even though some
256 methodological differences exist among them.

257 *3.2. Relations among word features*

258 *3.2. 1. Relations between dominance and affective variables*

259 Relative to valence and arousal, the dominance dimension has received little attention in
260 prior research since it accounts for a much smaller proportion of the variance of
261 emotion. Thus, it is not surprising that only few studies have investigated the relation
262 between dominance and the two other affective dimensions. Prior research has typically
263 observed a positive correlation between dominance and valence, with people feeling
264 more in control of words denoting pleasant concepts [6, 16, 8, 10, 12]. Results are more
265 inconsistent with regard to the dimension of arousal. In this sense, some studies found
266 that highly activating words were associated with high scores in dominance [10],
267 whereas others found the opposite pattern of results [12], or even a U-shape relation
268 between dominance and arousal [6, 12]. The results of these studies have some
269 theoretical implications for the debate concerning the orthogonality of the affective
270 dimensions, as it was first established by some authors [e.g., 1]. In order to add some
271 light to this debate, the relation between dominance values and the ratings for both
272 valence and arousal dimensions collected in our prior study [24] was explored in two
273 separate regression analyses, with either valence or arousal as the independent measure
274 and dominance as the dependent one. The linear and quadratic models were tested
275 separately.

276 The affective space defined by the valence and dominance dimensions is shown
277 in Fig 1. A high quadratic relationship between valence and dominance was found, $R =$
278 $.52$, $F(2,872) = 162.36$, $p < .001$, which explained 27,1% of the variance. The analysis
279 of the linear model showed no significant effects, $R = .03$, $F(1,873) = 0.84$, $p > .05$,
280 accounting only for 0.01% of the variance. The U-shape distribution indicates that
281 participants experienced a higher degree of control to concepts denoted by highly
282 pleasant and unpleasant words. Further analyses confirmed this finding by showing a
283 positive correlation between dominance and valence in pleasant words (mean valence

284 ratings > 6 ; $r = .39$, $p < .001$) and a negative correlation between dominance and
285 valence in negative words negative words (mean valence ratings < 4 ; $r = -.29$, $p < .001$).
286 With regard to the relation between dominance and arousal, both the linear [$R = .65$,
287 $F(1,873) = 632.39$, $p < .001$] and the quadratic [$R = .65$, $F(2,872) = 320.70$, $p < .001$]
288 models showed significant effects, accounting for a similar percentage of variance (42%
289 and 42,4%, respectively). Fig 2 shows the affective space defined by the valence and
290 dominance dimensions. Additional analyses showed a positive correlation between
291 dominance and arousal high arousal words (mean arousal ratings > 6 ; $r = .37$, $p < .001$).
292 In contrast, the correlation between dominance and arousal in low arousal words failed
293 to reach significance (mean arousal ratings < 4 ; $r = .004$, $p > .05$). Thus, it seems that
294 words associated with higher levels of activation were also experienced as being more
295 under the control of the participants. Finally, the relation between scores for dominance
296 and those collected in our previous normative study [24] for the discrete categories of
297 happiness, fear, anger, sadness and disgust was investigated. We observed a positive
298 correlation between dominance and all discrete emotions, with the highest values for
299 words associated to anger and fear concepts (see Table 2).

300 *** Fig 1 and 2 about here***

301

302 **Fig 1.** Quadratic distribution of scores for the 875 words in the affective space defined
303 by dominance and valence, for the total sample.

304 **Fig 2.** a) Linear and b) quadratic distributions of scores for the 875 words in the
305 affective space defined by dominance and arousal, for the total sample.

306

307

Table 2 Correlations between dominance (Dom), Familiarity (Fam), subjective age of acquisition (SAoA) and sensory experience ratings (SERs) and the affective variables of valence (Val), arousal (Aro) and the discrete emotions (happiness, Hap; anger, Ang; sadness, Sad; fear, Fea; disgust, Dis)

	Val	Aro	Dom	Hap	Ang	Sad	Fea	Dis
Dom	.031	.648*	1	.209*	.310*	.194*	.362*	.154*
Fam	.399*	.027	.236*	.426*	-.244*	-.232*	-.241*	-.271*
SAoA	-.270*	.019	.006	-.279*	.231*	.214*	.173*	.201*
SERs	.012	.525*	.490*	.235*	.239*	.300*	.339*	.232*

* $p < .001$

309

310 Overall, the results of the analyses showed a complex pattern of relationships
 311 between dominance and the affective variables. The finding of a quadratic relation
 312 between valence and dominance contrasts with prior research that reported a linear
 313 relation between these dimensions [6, 12] that is, high dominance in positive and low
 314 dominance in negative situations. Several factors may account for this discrepancy. It
 315 should be noted first that the correlations reported in a normative study reflect the
 316 structure of the specific words used [16]. In this sense, most of the words in our
 317 database were rated by the participants as having rather medium scores in the
 318 dominance dimension (464 out of 875 words showed values between 4 and 6; 236
 319 words were rated higher than 6; 175 words showed scores lower than 4), which may
 320 have undermined the relation between valence and dominance. Moreover, as has been
 321 pointed out by some authors [16] differences in rating instructions may influence
 322 dominance values. For instance, participants in the current study were instructed to
 323 score the dominant meaning of the words, whereas in other studies they rated their own
 324 feeling of control (e.g., [12]). Thus, following the argument of [16], a participant may
 325 consider a spider as having dominant meaning but feeling a low level of control. Also,
 326 the existence of cultural differences in the degree of control that people perceive over

327 affective experiences may not be totally disregarded. In this respect, dominance ratings
328 show greater variability across languages [6, 7]. Also, it has been suggested that
329 dominance scores show a higher sensibility to individual differences since this
330 dimension highlights the raters' subjective self-centered perspective and participants
331 rely more on their own coping strategies towards an object [10, 74]. Finally, it has been
332 shown that discrete specific that share a negative connotation may be related to very
333 different feelings of power or weakness [46]. In this sense, emotions such as anger have
334 been found to be opposed to sadness or shame in the dominance dimension. Thus,
335 divergent results in dominance ratings across normative studies could be partially
336 attributed to differences in the percentage of negative words belonging to these specific
337 emotions. Nonetheless, the finding of a positive correlation between arousal and
338 dominance replicates the results from previous studies [6, 16, 10]. Also, our data
339 matches those of the only prior study that assessed the relation between dominance and
340 discrete emotions in English words by showing that words rated with higher scores in
341 happiness, anger, sadness, fear and disgust are experienced as being more dominant
342 [26].

343 To summarize, it seems that results regarding the relation between dominance
344 and other affective variables should be taken with caution given the concerns mentioned
345 above (see [8] for extended discussion on this issue). Here, we provided evidence
346 suggesting that the relation between dominance and valence in a set of Spanish words
347 differs from that observed in Italian [6] Dutch [16] or English [12]. Thus, further
348 corpora are needed in different languages and including different sets of words in order
349 to clarify this issue. At a theoretical level, the finding of a significant relation between
350 dominance and discrete emotions suggests that it is important to design studies that

351 consider the scores in affective categories and dimensions in order to further develop
352 the claims made by both dimensional and basic emotion proposals [24, 26]).

353 *3.2.2. Relations between psycholinguistics and affective variables*

354 We also explored the influence of ratings collected for familiarity, subjective AoA and
355 sensory experience on the assessments of the affective content of words. To this end,
356 Pearson correlation coefficients were computed between these psycholinguistic
357 variables and dominance scores found in the current study. Ratings on psycholinguistics
358 variables were also correlated with those collected in our previous study for the values
359 of the affective dimensions of valence and arousal, as well as for the emotional
360 categories of happiness, anger, sadness, fear and disgust. The results of these analyses
361 are summarized in Table 2.

362 Familiarity values showed significant positive correlations with scores in
363 valence, suggesting that more familiar words also tend to denote positive concepts. We
364 also found a positive correlation between familiarity and dominance. Thus, participants
365 felt more control when they assessed words that occur more often in everyday language.
366 In contrast, no significant correlation was found for familiarity and arousal. Although
367 familiarity is thought to be more language specific than other lexical variables [17], the
368 relation between familiarity and affective dimensions closely replicates the results from
369 previous studies [6, 22, 12]. These findings have been interpreted to reflect an adaptive
370 tendency to feel threatened and to perceive lower control when dealing with something
371 unfamiliar [6]. In agreement with this view, we observed a positive significant
372 correlation between familiarity and happiness while negative significant correlations
373 were found with anger, sadness, fear and disgust.

374 Subjective AoA had a negative correlation with valence, whereas no significant
375 correlations were found with either arousal or dominance. This finding suggests that

376 words rated as denoting more pleasant concepts are learned early in life. Similar
377 findings have been reported by [16], although a positive correlation between subjective
378 AoA and dominance was also found in their study. In contrast, [11] only found a
379 relation between subjective AoA and arousal. Again, divergences could be explained by
380 differences in language characteristics, stimulus sets and sample peculiarities. Notably,
381 the relation between subjective AoA and affective dimensions has been the subject of
382 just the two above mentioned studies, so future research will provide additional clues on
383 this issue. Regarding discrete emotions, subjective AoA showed a negative correlation
384 with happiness, while positive correlations were observed for angry, sad, fearful and
385 disgusting words. Thus, our data indicate a learning advantage for happy words,
386 whereas words related to negative discrete categories are learnt later in life.
387 Taken together, prior results suggesting the contribution of AoA to word recognition
388 times [33] and those found in the current study highlight the importance of controlling
389 the effects of this variable in studies concerned with the processing of affective
390 language.

391 Finally, SERs showed a positive correlation with arousal and dominance, which
392 suggests that more activating and dominant words also evoke a richer sensory and
393 perceptual experience. Interestingly, although our results indicate a lack of relation
394 between SERs and valence, positive correlations between SERs and all five discrete
395 emotions were found. Thus, words associated with more vivid sensorial attributes are
396 also those rated with higher scores on happiness, anger, sadness, fear and disgust.
397 The close relation observed between SERs and both arousal and dominance, on the one
398 hand, and between SERs and emotional categories, on the other hand, may be of
399 particular interest for those researches conducting investigations under the embodied
400 cognition framework. In this sense, our data may be suitable for investigating sensory

401 activation elicited by pleasant and unpleasant words. The current results may also have
402 some theoretical implications for the status of SERs. It should be mentioned that in our
403 prior study we found relations between concreteness and both valence and arousal, as
404 well as with ratings in anger, sadness, fear and disgust. Notably, the divergent pattern of
405 relationships between concreteness or SERs and affective variables, provides indirect
406 evidence for the idea that these psycholinguistic variables may rely on different
407 perceptual attributes, even though both concepts are conceptually related. In this
408 respect, SERs showed a positive correlation with concreteness scores obtained in our
409 prior normative study, $r = .30, p < .001$, indicating that words associated with more
410 sensory experiences were also perceived as denoting more concrete concepts.
411 Nonetheless, it has been pointed out that concreteness and imageability tend to stress
412 visual and sound properties, whereas SERs may be associated with a broader set of
413 sensorial modalities, including smells, odors and tastes [62, 63].

414 Overall, it seems that familiarity, subjective AoA and SERs have distinct
415 relations with the affective properties of the words, which highlight the complex pattern
416 of interactions between different emotional and psycholinguistic features found in prior
417 studies. Our data also emphasizes the importance of taking into account these variables
418 when investigating affective language and formulating theoretical models of emotional
419 language processing.

420 **4. Conclusion**

421 The present normative study expands the MADS by incorporating ratings for an
422 affective dimension and three psycholinguistic variables. Thus, researches interested in
423 investigating affective language have now available a corpus of 875 words that includes
424 norms for three affective dimensions –valence, arousal and dominance–, five discrete
425 emotions –happiness, anger, sadness, fear and disgust–, four subjective psycholinguistic

426 variables –concreteness, familiarity, subjective AoA and SERs–, and two objective
427 psycholinguistic variables –word frequency and word length–. Furthermore, the results
428 of our analyses confirmed the relations between affective dimensions and both
429 familiarity and subjective AoA observed in prior studies in other languages. Notably,
430 we reported here for the first time relations between these two psycholinguistic
431 variables and discrete emotional categories, as well as between SERs and emotional
432 variables. In sum, the new data should facilitate the design of empirical experiments that
433 investigate the precise contribution of these psycholinguistic features to the processing
434 of affective language.

435

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438

439 **Appendix**

440 The original rating instructions given to the participants, as well as their corresponding
441 English translations, can be found below:

442 *A continuación se presenta una lista de palabras en el que te pedimos que por favor*
443 *evalúes en las siguientes escalas:*

444 Hereafter you will be presented with a list of words that we ask you to rate in the
445 following scales:

446 - *El grado de **familiaridad**: debes valorar con qué frecuencia te encuentras estas*
447 *palabras en el lenguaje cotidiano, tanto en forma oral como escrita. Debes realizar tu*
448 *juicio usando una escala de 1 a 9. Una puntuación de 1 indica que casi nunca te*
449 *encuentras la palabra en el lenguaje cotidiano, mientras que una de 9 indica que casi*
450 *siempre te encuentras la palabra en el uso cotidiano del lenguaje.*

451 - The degree of **familiarity**: you should consider how frequently you find these words
452 in your day-to-day language, both in oral and written form. You should make your
453 judgment using a scale from 1 to 9. A score of 1 means that you almost never find that
454 word in ordinary language, while a score of 9 means that you almost always find that
455 word in ordinary language.

456 - *El nivel de **dominancia**: aquí debes valorar en qué medida cada palabra se refiere*
457 *a algo débil/sumiso o a algo fuerte/dominante, usando una escala de 1 a 9. Una*
458 *puntuación de 1 indica que es muy débil/sumiso, mientras que un 9 se refiere a algo*
459 *muy fuerte/dominante. A continuación tienes una representación pictórica de la escala.*

460 - The degree of **dominance**: here you should rate how much a Word is referring to
461 something weak/submissive or to something strong/dominant, using a scale from 1 to 9.
462 A score of 1 means that something is very weak/submissive, while a 9 is referring to
463 something very strong/dominant. Below you will find a pictorial representation of the
464 scale.

465 - *La **edad de adquisición** de la palabra: se refiere a la edad desde la que estimas que*
466 *conoces la palabra. Debes hacer tu valoración usando una escala con distintos rangos*
467 *que van desde menos de 2 años hasta 11 años o más.*

468 - The **age of acquisition** of the word: refers to the age at which you estimate that you
469 learnt the Word. You should give your rating using a scale ranging from less than 2
470 years old to 11 years old or older.

471 - *La **experiencia sensorial**: debes valorar el nivel de experiencia sensorial que*
472 *te evoca cada palabra. Se refiere a una sensación real (sabor, tacto, vista, sonido, u*
473 *olor) que experimentas cuando lees la palabra. Debes hacer tu valoración usando una*
474 *escala de 1 a 7, donde 1 significa que no te evoca ninguna experiencia sensorial y 7*
475 *significa que evoca una muy fuerte experiencia sensorial.*

476 - The **sensory experience**: you should judge the level of sensory experience that each of
477 the words evokes in you. That means a real sensation (taste, touch, sight, sound, or
478 smell) that you experiment when you read the word. You should give your rating using
479 a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means that it does not evoke any sensory experience at all
480 and 7 means that it evokes a very strong sensory experience.

481 *Selecciona sólo una respuesta por palabra en cada escala y recuerda que no hay*
482 *respuestas correctas o incorrectas.*

483 Select only one answer per word in each of the scales and remember that there is no
484 right or wrong answer.

485

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703 [Table 1.](#) Descriptive stimulus characteristics.

704 Dominance Familiarity Subjective AoA SERs

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Mean	5.13	5.78	7.07	3.9
<i>SD</i>	1.20	1.16	2.16	0.8
Mini mum	2.27	2.24	1.53	1.4
Maxi mum	8.33	8.60	10.88	6.2
Rang e	6.06	6.36	9.35	4.7

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719 [Table 2](#). Correlations between dominance (Dom), Familiarity (Fam), subjective age of
 720 acquisition (SAoA) and sensory experience ratings (SERs) and the affective variables of
 721 valence (Val), arousal (Aro) and the discrete emotions (happiness, Hap; anger, Ang;
 722 sadness, Sad; fear, Fea; disgust, Dis).

723

724 Val Aro Dom Hap Ang Sad Fea Dis

725

Dom	.031	.648*	1	.209*	.310*	.194*	.362*	.1
Fam	.399*	.027	.236*	.426*	-.244*	-.232*	-.241*	-.1
SAoA	-.270*	.019	.006	-.279*	.231*	.214*	.173*	.2
SERs	.012	.525*	.490*	.235*	.239*	.300*	.339*	.2

726 * $p < .001$

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740 Figure 1

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